

Reading Proficiency of Grade 4 Learners in Relation to their Academic Performance

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Abstract:

Reading proficiency and academic performance are essential to a learner's academic success. This study aimed to determine the level of reading proficiency of Grade 4 learners with their academic performance in a district cluster, in a large-sized school division in Central Philippines, for the school year 2022-2023. It employed a descriptive method utilizing a standardized PHIL-IRI reading instrument on 162 Grade 4 learners. Findings revealed that the reading proficiency of Grade 4 learners is frustrated. When grouped and compared according to sex, average family monthly income, and number of siblings, the level of reading proficiency was at the frustration level; yet, as to average family monthly income, it was at the instructional level for the higher group. Furthermore, their level of academic performance was satisfactory, even when grouped according to the aforementioned variables. Generally, no significant difference existed in the level of reading proficiency except for noting details according to parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and number of siblings, and making inferences as to the number of siblings. Also, there is no significant difference in the level of academic performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Finally, there is a significant relationship between the level of reading proficiency of Grade 4 learners and their level of academic performance. Hence, the study inferred that their reading proficiency can influence academic performance. Thus, it is recommended that intervention programs be focused on strengthening every learner's reading proficiency and academic performance.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Learners, Reading Proficiency

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Republic Act No. 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, empowers the Department of Education (DepEd) to implement policies and programs to enhance basic education, including literacy efforts like the Every Child A Reader Program (ECARP). In line with this, DepEd Order No. 45, s. 2002 launched the Reading Literacy Program to improve reading proficiency among Grades 3 and 4 students and boost academic performance. To support these initiatives, DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2018 mandates the use of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI), a standardized tool for assessing students' reading abilities.

Reading proficiency involves key skills such as noting details, making inferences, predicting, generalizing, and sequencing, all of which contribute to decoding, fluency, vocabulary, comprehension, and critical thinking—factors essential to academic success. As a foundational skill for learning other subjects, reading targets comprehension, which engages both cognitive and linguistic processes. Strong reading comprehension significantly influences academic performance, defined as the degree to which learners achieve educational goals, especially critical in Grade 4, a transitional stage where English becomes the primary medium of instruction.

Observations reveal that Grade 4 learners at the research site struggle with English reading comprehension, particularly in prediction, noting details, inference, and generalization, likely due to limited background knowledge and use of English as a second language, which may hinder their self-correction strategies. These challenges prompted the researcher to investigate the learners' level of reading comprehension skills in English and how these affect their academic performance.

Current State of Knowledge

The ability to identify the main idea in a text is a crucial component of reading comprehension, as it helps learners distinguish between essential and non-essential information and recognize key ideas and supporting details.

According to Harris et al. (2019), inference skills are equally vital, allowing students to read with proficiency, accuracy, and understanding by engaging thoughtfully with textual content. Inferences involve transforming explicit information into new insights, either by generating previously unavailable information (induction) or by clarifying implicit content (deduction), as explained by Wallis (2020). Additionally, prediction is a significant reading strategy that enhances comprehension by encouraging learners to anticipate outcomes based on textual clues, engage actively with the content, and form meaningful connections—ultimately improving their overall understanding of the material (Lynch, 2021).

These core reading strategies—inferring, predicting, and identifying main ideas—are also evident in the context of Filipino learners. Among them, inference relies heavily on prior knowledge and contextual clues, making texts more engaging and memorable (Duffy et al., 2017). However, the effectiveness of these strategies can be shaped by external factors. For instance, while prediction skills positively impact comprehension in experimental settings, they do not always produce the same results in standard classroom environments (Anyienda et al., 2020). Moreover, socioeconomic disparities strongly influence reading ability; students from lower-income families often face greater reading challenges due to a lack of awareness and support at home (Mahamod et al., 2021). This is reinforced by findings that students from wealthier families and those with more educated parents tend to score higher in reading comprehension (Çiğdemiri & Akyolii, 2022), and that girls and private school students generally outperform their peers. Interestingly, teacher-led reading comprehension strategies showed limited effect on average performance.

Supporting this, Fabelaa and Abaoag (2023) reported that many pupils remain at a frustration reading level, with males outperforming females, and those from La Union exhibiting better reading proficiency than those from Pangasinan. Home-related factors, particularly parental education, continue to play a vital role. Torres (2019) emphasized that children of parents with only elementary education often struggle with reading, while those with well-educated parents receive more academic support. Cadiz-Gabejan and Quirino (2021) similarly found that reading proficiency is affected by sex, parental background, and school attendance, and directly correlates with academic performance. Furthermore, students performed best in identifying main ideas and weakest in noting details, suggesting differences in cognitive skill development (Suson et al., 2020). Tagaytay (2021) affirmed the strong link between reading comprehension and academic performance in English, especially among Grade IV pupils.

Pinero and Canedo's (2024) study adds nuance by showing no significant difference in noting details based on sex but finding significant variation based on the number of siblings, as well as parents' education and income levels. However, when it comes to making inferences, there were no significant differences observed across these same demographic variables, emphasizing that different aspects of reading comprehension may be influenced by different factors.

Understanding reading proficiency also requires examining its relationship to academic performance. Academic performance is typically defined as the achievement of educational goals measured by tests, grades, and outputs (Tadese et al., 2022; Magulod, 2019). Influencing factors include not only cognitive and learning skills but also environmental elements like home support and study habits. In the Philippine context, performance is assessed through final grades, with 75% as the minimum passing mark (Oclaret, 2021).

Socioeconomic status continues to play a dominant role in academic achievement. Sumugat and Caraballe (2021) highlighted that family income more significantly affects student performance than other variables, reinforcing the broader issue of poverty's impact on education. Agiboshim and Obina (2023) added that elder siblings often perform better academically than their younger counterparts, though family socioeconomic status did not show a statistically significant influence. Alcoriza (2021) also found improved academic performance among Grade 4 pupils during the pandemic, though math remained a challenge.

However, the relationship between reading and academic performance is complex. Viduya and Antonio (2022) found no significant correlation between reading comprehension and academic performance among Grade 6 pupils. Conversely, Lasaten and Racca (2016) observed that stronger English language proficiency significantly enhanced student performance across English, Math, and Science. Supporting this, Iman (2016) argued that while reading comprehension is important, it does not fully account for poor Math and Science performance, especially given the different predictors at play in public versus private schools.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is grounded in three key theories: the Simple View of Reading (Gough & Tunmer, 1986), Schema Theory (Bartlett, 1932), and the Theory of Academic Performance (Elger, 2007). The Simple View of Reading posits that reading comprehension results from the combination of decoding (accurately reading words) and language comprehension (understanding spoken language). If either skill is lacking, comprehension fails. This framework is especially relevant in identifying and supporting struggling readers, as both decoding and understanding are essential for academic success. Schema Theory, on the other hand, highlights that meaning is not derived solely from text but is constructed through the interaction between the reader's background knowledge and the text itself. Efficient

comprehension involves connecting prior knowledge with new information through skills like noting details, making inferences, and generalizing—skills that are crucial for Grade 4 learners developing English reading proficiency. Complementing these is Elger's Theory of Academic Performance, which explains that performance depends on factors such as context, knowledge, skills, identity, and personal and fixed factors. Improvement in academic performance requires a positive mindset, an enriching environment, and active engagement in reflective practice. In educational settings, academic performance is typically measured through tests and assessments, but true performance growth involves learning that leads to meaningful results. This theory supports the idea that enhancing reading comprehension is not only about skill development but also about fostering an environment and mindset conducive to academic growth. All three theories collectively underpin this study's focus on understanding and improving the reading comprehension and academic performance of Grade 4 learners.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of reading comprehension skills in the English language and its impact on the academic performance of Grade 4 learners of a school in a district of a large division in Central Philippines for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this research sought to answer the following: 1) the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, Parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and number of siblings; 2) the level of reading comprehension skills in the English Language of the Grade 4 learners in the area of noting details, making inferences, predicting outcomes, making generalizations, and sequencing; 3) the reading comprehension level in the English language of the Grade 4 learners when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 4) level of academic performance of Grade 4 learners for the school year 2022-2023, when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 5) the significant difference in the level of reading comprehension in the English language of the Grade 4 learners when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; 6) the significant difference in the level of academic performance of Grade 4 learners for the school year 2022-2023 when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and 7) the significant relationship between the level of reading comprehension in the English language and the level of academic performance of Grade 4 learners.

Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study used descriptive research design to determine the level of reading proficiency of Grade 4 learners in relation to their academic performance in a cluster of a district, in a large-sized division in Central Philippines for the school year 2022-2023.

According to McCombes (2019) descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population being studied; it does not describe what caused a situation. What is used under descriptive method is a survey approach which is normally used to explore opinions according to respondents that can represent a whole population.

Descriptive Method is used in this research as it was aimed at collecting information and determining relationships without making any changes to the research topic, as its main concern is to determine and report the way things are.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 162 Grade 4 learners. The researcher employed purposive sampling in determining the respondents. According to Alchemer (2020), purposive sampling is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys.

Instruments

The study utilized a pre-validated reading selection from the 2018 Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) Manual, with a questionnaire divided into two parts: Part I collected demographic data (sex, parents' education, income, and number of siblings), while Part II assessed reading comprehension through five skill areas—noting details, making inferences, predicting outcomes, making generalizations, and sequencing—each with 10 items scored based on PHIL-IRI's quantification levels (Independent, Instructional, and Frustration). Content validity was ensured through expert evaluation by three education professionals, incorporating their suggestions into the final version; the instrument achieved a validity mean score of 4.74, rated as excellent. Reliability was established using the KR-

20 method, yielding a reliability index of 0.799 from a pilot test with 30 non-respondent Grade 4 learners, indicating the instrument was consistent and acceptable for use.

Data Gathering Procedure

In order to collect the data, formal letters of permission were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent for his consent to allow data collection at the target respondents. When his notice of agreement was returned, the researcher started conducting the reading test. It was a silent reading test of which materials were distributed to the respondents through the parents who got and returned the modules. After retrieving all questionnaires, the researcher checked in order to generate each respondent's score. After the collection of data, they were organized for statistical interpretation.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 utilized descriptive analytical scheme and frequency count and simple percentage formula to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and number of siblings.

Objective No. 2 utilized descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of reading proficiency of Grade 4 learners in the English language in terms of noting details, making inferences, predicting outcome, making generalization and sequencing.

Objective No. 3 employed descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of reading proficiency of Grade 4 learners in the English language when grouped according to the variables.

Objective No. 4 employed descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of academic performance of Grade 4 learners for the school year 2022-2023 when grouped according to the variables.

Objective No. 5 employed the comparative analytical scheme and independent samples t-test to determine the significant difference in the level of reading proficiency of the Grade 4 learners when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Objective No. 6 employed the comparative analytical scheme and independent samples t-test to determine the significant difference in the level of reading proficiency of Grade 4 learners for the school year 2022-2023 when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Objective No. 7 used the relational analytical scheme and Pearson r correlation to determine the significant relationship between the level of reading proficiency and the level of academic performance of Grade 4 learners.

Ethical Consideration

Key ethical principles guiding the use of human participants and minors were strictly adhered to in the study. These included providing the teachers, parents, and students with the necessary information to make a determination as to whether they want (the students) to be part of the study. The signing of the consent form, which is actually a process rather than an event was not used as coercive tool to compel participants to complete the study. They were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any point when they became uncomfortable with the study. The identity of the children as well as their responses was kept confidential such that neither the responses nor their identity was revealed to any other person outside the research team.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Variables Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	89	54.90
	Female	73	45.10

Parents' Educational Attainment	Highest	Lower (Elementary Level)	87	53.70
		Higher (High School Level and above)	75	46.30
Average Monthly Income	Family	Lower (below 4,500 pesos)	59	36.40
		Higher (4,500 pesos and above)	103	63.60
Number of Siblings		Few (below 3)	58	35.80
		Many (3 and above)	104	64.20
Total			162	100.00

Table 1 presents the table of respondents. As shown in the table, there are 89 or 54.90 percent male and 73 or 45.10 percent female as to sex grouping. This implies that in terms of sex, there are more male respondents than female respondents. This is similar to the result of Miñoza and Montero (2019), that there are more male than female respondents in their study. However, the difference is negligible.

Regarding parents' highest educational attainment, 87, or 53.70 percent, belonged to the lower category, while 75, or 46.30 percent, belonged to the higher category. More parents were at the elementary level only. This indicates that the parents of the respondents were progressive in education. However, they were still far from higher education, which is important today to create a knowledge-based society. This may prove that parents may fail to support their children in education, as they have only attained a lower education. The study of Tumarong (2023) has similar results because it was revealed in her study that most of the respondents' parents attained only an elementary level, with a frequency.

The average family monthly income below 4,500 pesos was lower at 59 or 36.40 percent, and 4,500 pesos and above was higher at 103 or 53.60 percent. This shows that most of the family's monthly income was meager. This is probably different from the results of the study of Miñoza and Montero (2019), where there is an equal number of respondents who belong to low and average socio-economic status, and respondents who belong to a high socio-economic status are the least.

Regarding the number of siblings, only 58, or 35.80 percent, had fewer than three siblings, while 104, or 64.20 percent, had many siblings. This opposes the findings of Pinero and Canedo (2024) that there were more with few siblings than with many siblings.

Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details, Making Inferences, Predicting Outcomes, Making Generalizations, and Sequencing

Table 2

Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details, Making Inferences, Predicting Outcomes, Making Generalizations, and Sequencing

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
Noting Details	65.93	Instructional Level
Making Inferences	59.88	Instructional Level
Predicting Outcomes	53.00	Frustration Level
Making Generalization	47.04	Frustration Level
Sequencing	54.90	Frustration Level

Table 2 discloses the level of reading proficiency in the five areas considered in this study.

A closer look at the result of the noting details shows that the respondents obtained a mean score of 65.93, or an instructional level. This result indicates that the learners have adequate background knowledge of a topic and can access text with few errors in understanding basic information that elicits ideas or meaning directly mentioned in the selection. This contradicts the result of Ancheta's (2018) study, which found that more than fifty percent of the students are low in noting details.

According to Johnson (1991), as cited by Estremera et al. (2018), reading comprehension is the construction of bridges between the "new and the unknown" and the necessity of past knowledge. Indeed, prior knowledge is critical for comprehension to flow easily from simple to complex. Learners who truly comprehend are better equipped to ask insightful, specific questions and answer detailed ones. According to the Cognitive Load Theory, readers who focus on relevant details reduce extraneous cognitive load, making comprehension easier (Sweller, 1988).

The respondents obtained a mean of 59.88 on the instructional level of making inferences. This result indicates that learners have average abilities in comprehending ideas embedded between and among the lines and interpreting the meanings implied in the passage. This does not support the result of Ancheta's (2018) study, where a significant percentage of the students performed low in inferring ability. However, the result confirms that of Warnidah et al. (2016), the students' overall difficulty in making inferences in reading narrative passages belonged to the moderate category.

Regarding predicting outcomes, the respondents achieved a frustration level with a mean score of 53.00. The result shows that the students' ability to make predictions and evaluate is poor. They cannot judge how the ideas and meanings are presented in the selection. This result also lends credence to information regarding respondents' reading comprehension level in making predictions, as Ancheta (2018) provided that most of the students performed poorly in predicting outcomes.

While making generalizations, the respondents obtained a mean result of 47.04, or frustration level. This means that learners need to be given attention to the skills of generalizing ideas from texts read. According to Estremera and Estremera (2018), it is noticeable that, in conclusion, Grade 6 pupils are frustrated as they withdraw from reading situations, refusing to read.

In sequencing, the mean result obtained was 54.90, or frustration level. Grade 5 learners may struggle with sequencing due to increased text complexity, which demands stronger comprehension and memory skills. Additionally, limited vocabulary can make it harder to identify and organize the order of events. This result conforms to Piñero & Cañedo (2024), who state that learners are frustrated with the sequencing construct.

It is evident in the results that the highest mean is 65.93, or the instructional level for noting details. However, it is generalizing that the respondents obtained the lowest mean, 47.04. This means that among the areas considered in this study, learners often struggle with generalizing in reading because it requires higher-order thinking skills and prompts them to conclude that they find challenging.

According to Estremera and Estremera (2018), it is noticeable that when making conclusions, pupils are at a frustration level as they withdraw from reading situations and refuse to read. This connotes that learners have not developed their higher-order thinking skills and that most are struggling readers. This finding supports the finding that most students belonged to the frustration level of reading proficiency, especially in silent reading (Cabardo, 2015; Amorganda & Olores, 2024; Fabella & Abaoag, 2023). Moreover, this result is similar to that of Imam et al. (2014), which showed that overall students' performance in reading proficiency was indexed at a low mastery level.

Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details, Making Inferences, Predicting Outcomes, Making Generalizations, and Sequencing when grouped according to Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings

Table 3

Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details, Making Inferences, Predicting Outcomes, Making Generalizations, and Sequencing when grouped according to Sex

Areas	Male	Interpretation	Female	Interpretation
	Mean		Mean	
Noting Details	67.63	Instructional Level	63.85	Instructional Level
Making Inferences	60.26	Instructional Level	59.42	Instructional Level
Predicting Outcomes	55.20	Frustration Level	50.32	Frustration Level
Making Generalization	48.06	Frustration Level	45.81	Frustration Level
Sequencing	54.93	Frustration Level	54.86	Frustration Level

Table 3 shows the level of reading proficiency when grouped according to sex. Males had higher mean results than females in reading proficiency, though both were frustrated. This result contradicts that females outperform males regarding reading proficiency (Miñoza & Montero, 2019; Nyarko et al., 2018).

Moreover, Bekdas (2015) shows that females had higher results in the foreign language test and had higher linguistic intelligence than males. Also, males are less proficient in reading than females in silent and oral reading (Cabardo, 2015). However, gender was not found to play an important role in reading performance (Vlachos & Papadimitriou, 2015). However, the result supports Fabella and Abaoag's (2023) study, which revealed that males are better readers than females.

Further, in predicting outcomes, the two groups differed significantly in the mean results; males had a mean score of 55.20 while females had 50.32, though both are interpreted as frustration level. Male learners may be more inclined to predict outcomes because they are more risk-takers than females. However, since their reading proficiency

is still at the frustration level, there is a need to balance prediction and careful comprehension strategies to help both male and female learners improve their reading proficiency and move beyond frustration levels.

In line with this finding, females are more proficient than males in predicting outcomes, according to the study by Matějů and Smith (2015).

Table 4

Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details, Making Inferences, Predicting Outcomes, Making Generalizations, and Sequencing when grouped according to Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Areas	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
Noting Details	61.75	Instructional Level	70.77	Instructional Level
Making Inferences	57.55	Frustration Level	62.59	Instructional Level
Predicting Outcomes	52.57	Frustration Level	53.49	Frustration Level
Making Generalization	44.87	Frustration Level	49.56	Frustration Level
Sequencing	53.26	Frustration Level	56.80	Frustration Level

Table 4 presents the data on the level of reading proficiency when grouped according to parents' highest educational attainment. The respondents whose parents belonged to the lower category obtained a mean of 54.00, interpreted as frustration level. In comparison, those in the higher category obtained a mean score of 58.64, which is interpreted as an instructional level. This indicates that respondents with parents who belonged to high school and college levels can give more assistance and have enough knowledge to bestow on their children to help them improve their reading proficiency level.

Further, parents who attained high school or college education are more likely to have developed reading skills, knowledge, and strategies they can share with their children. This advantage may enhance their capacity to guide, encourage, and provide resources to enhance reading proficiency.

This confirms Torres (2019), who found that learners whose parents' educational level had only attained elementary education have poor reading proficiency.

Table 5

Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details, Making Inferences, Predicting Outcomes, Making Generalizations, and Sequencing when grouped according to Average Family Monthly Income

Areas	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
Noting Details	61.42	Instructional Level	68.50	Instructional Level
Making Inferences	56.85	Frustration Level	61.62	Instructional Level
Predicting Outcomes	54.78	Frustration Level	51.98	Instructional Level
Making Generalization	48.54	Frustration Level	46.18	Frustration Level
Sequencing	53.15	Frustration Level	55.90	Frustration Level

Table 5 shows the level of reading proficiency according to noting details, making inferences, predicting outcomes, making generalizations, and sequencing when grouped according to average family monthly income. The lower and higher groups, regarding average family monthly income, had mean results of 54.95 and 56.84, respectively. The lower group, having obtained lower mean results, confirms that most students who struggle with reading skills come from low-income families who are less aware of the importance of reading (Mahamod et al., 2021).

By inspecting the results obtained by each area, it is evident that the two groups varied greatly in their mean results in note-taking, with 61.42 for the lower group and 68.50 for the higher group, both interpreted as Instructional level. Learners from lower-income families often have limited access to resources and educational support, making it harder to focus and practice organizing and recording key information or ideas from written texts.

Truly, family income can play a role in providing access to resources and educational opportunities. The result of this study is similar to that of Chen et al. (2018), which showed that complicated linguistic mechanisms are involved in the link between parental socio-economic position and students' reading ability.

Table 6

Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details, Making Inferences, Predicting Outcomes, Making Generalizations, and Sequencing when grouped according to Number of Siblings

Areas	Few Mean	Interpretation	Many Mean	Interpretation
Noting Details	74.03	Instructional Level	61.40	Instructional Level
Making Inferences	67.14	Instructional Level	55.84	Frustration Level
Predicting Outcomes	54.36	Instructional Level	52.24	Frustration Level
Making Generalization	48.78	Frustration Level	46.08	Frustration Level
Sequencing	58.93	Frustration Level	52.65	Frustration Level

Table 6 presents the level of reading proficiency according to noting details, making inferences, predicting outcomes, making generalizations, and sequencing when grouped according to the number of siblings. Veering closely, it is evident that it is in noting details where the mean scores display a greater difference. Those with few siblings got 74.03, and those with many children got 61.40; both were interpreted as instructional level. The result suggests that learners with fewer siblings may receive more attention and support from any family member, allowing more support in developing the skill of noting details. In contrast, those with many siblings might experience divided attention and fewer individualized learning opportunities, affecting their ability to focus on and retain detailed information.

Such a result supported that of Keller et al. (2015), who discovered that the more siblings a child has, the poorer their second language proficiency. On the contrary, Prime et al. (2014) showed that learners with many siblings had greater opportunities to develop reading skills with their older siblings.

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 4 Learners for the First and Second Quarters of the School Year 2022-2023

Table 7

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 4 Learners for the First and Second Quarters of the School Year 2022-2023

Variable	N	Mean	Interpretation
Academic Performance	162	82.62	Satisfactory

Table 7 presents the level of academic performance of Grade 4 learners for the first and second quarters of the school year 2022-2023. The table shows that the Grade 4 learners obtained a mean score of 82.62, interpreted as satisfactory. This indicates that the learners have acquired adequate knowledge and skills in the subject areas they have studied but may still have room for improvement to reach higher levels of understanding and mastery. This finding supports that of Alcoriza's (2021) study, which revealed that the overall academic performance of Grade 4 pupils was rated as satisfactory.

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 4 Learners for the First and Second Quarters of the School Year 2022-2023 when grouped according to Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings

Table 8

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 4 Learners for the First and Second Quarters of the School Year 2022-2023 when grouped according to Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings

Variable	Categories	Mean	Interpretation
Sex	Male	82.87	Satisfactory
	Female	82.32	Satisfactory
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	81.59	Satisfactory
	Higher	83.81	Satisfactory
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	82.08	Satisfactory
	Higher	82.92	Satisfactory
Number of Siblings	Few	84.24	Satisfactory
	Many	81.71	Satisfactory

Table 8 reveals the level of academic performance of Grade 4 learners for the first and second quarters of the school year 2022-2023 when grouped according to sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and number of siblings. It is evident from the table that all mean results are at a satisfactory level concerning the grouping variables considered. As to sex, males had 82.87. Females had 82.32. Regarding parents' highest educational attainment, the lower group had 81.59 and the higher group had 83.81. When grouped according to

average family monthly income, the lower group obtained 82.08, and the higher group obtained 82.92. When grouped by number of siblings, those with few siblings obtained 84.24, and those with many had 81.71.

Having all results satisfactory implies that sex, parents' level of education, household income, and the number of siblings do not play a substantial role in determining how well students perform academically. This aligns with the study of Asgarabadi (2015), which shows that slight variations in the trend can be seen regarding sex, the elementary education of parents, and grade level grouping.

Upon closer examination, it becomes clear that when grouped according to several siblings, the mean results for academic performance differ more than the rest of the variables: 84.24 for the group with few siblings and 81.71 for the group with many siblings; both are satisfactory. This may be because having fewer siblings allows more parental attention and resources to be devoted to each child, potentially enhancing academic performance. This aligns with the result of Aguboshim and Obinna's (2023) study, which shows that the mean academic performance of those with fewer siblings was higher than that of those with many siblings.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details, Making Inferences, Predicting Outcomes, Making Generalizations, and Sequencing, when grouped and compared according to Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, and Average Family Monthly Income

Table 9

Difference in the Level of Reading Proficiency according to Noting Details when grouped and compared according to Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings.

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	89	67.63	1.296	.197		Not Significant
	Female	73	63.85				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	87	61.75	-3.154	.002	0.05	Significant
	Higher	75	70.77				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	59	61.42	-2.426	.017		Significant
	Higher	103	68.50				
Number of Siblings	Few	58	74.03	4.206	.000		Significant
	Many	104	61.40				

Table 9 reveals no significant difference in Grade 4 learners' reading proficiency in noting details based on sex, but significant differences exist when grouped by parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and number of siblings. Learners with parents who have higher education and those from wealthier families tend to perform better, likely due to more supportive learning environments and greater access to resources. Additionally, students with fewer siblings show higher proficiency, possibly benefiting from more focused parental attention and less competition for resources. These findings align with Piñero and Cañedo (2024) and Cabardo (2015), confirming that sex does not significantly affect reading detail skills, while family background and sibling number do.

Table 10

Difference in the Level of Reading Proficiency According to Making Inferences When Grouped and Compared According to Sex, Parents' Highest Educational Attainment, and Average Family Monthly Income

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	89	60.26	.315	.753		Not Significant
	Female	73	59.42				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	87	57.55	-1.896	.060	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	75	62.59				
	Lower	59	56.85	-1.810	.073		Not Significant

Average Monthly Income	Family	Higher	103	61.62			
Number of Siblings	of	Few	58	67.14	4.398	.000	Significant
		Many	104	55.84			

Table 10 shows no significant difference in Grade 4 learners’ reading proficiency in making inferences based on sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, or average family monthly income, as all p-values exceeded 0.05. However, a significant difference was found when grouped by number of siblings, with learners having fewer siblings performing better, likely due to greater access to reading resources and individualized attention. This suggests that while demographic factors like gender and family background have little impact on inference skills, sibling count influences learners’ ability to engage in critical cognitive processes during reading. These findings align with Piñero and Cañedo (2024) on most variables but contrast regarding sibling influence and differ from Collins-Lisell (2015), who reported gender differences in inference-making.

Table 11

Difference in the Level of Reading Proficiency according to Predicting Outcomes when grouped and compared according to Sex, Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings.

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	89	55.20	1.656	.100	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	73	50.32				
Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	87	52.57	-.310	.757	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	75	53.49				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	59	54.78	.950	.344	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	103	51.98				
Number of Siblings	Few	58	54.36	.645	.521	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	104	52.24				

Table 11 shows no significant difference in Grade 4 learners’ reading proficiency in predicting outcomes when grouped by sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, or number of siblings, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that these demographic factors do not directly affect learners’ ability to predict outcomes, which is likely shaped more by critical thinking skills, prior reading experience, and the content of the text rather than external influences. This finding contrasts with Anyienda et al. (2020), who reported significant differences in prediction skills based on sex and family income.

Table 12

Difference in the Level of Reading Proficiency According to Making Generalizations When Grouped and Compared According to Sex, Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings.

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	89	48.06	.702	.484	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	73	45.81				
Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	87	44.87	-1.479	.141	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	75	49.56				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	59	48.54	.750	.454	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	103	46.18				
	Few	58	48.78	.791	.430	0.05	Not Significant

Number Siblings	of	Many	104	46.08
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Table 12 reveals no significant difference in Grade 4 learners’ reading proficiency in making generalizations across groups based on sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, or number of siblings, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance level. Both males and females showed similar abilities in generalizing information, and factors such as parental education, family income, and sibling number did not significantly influence this skill. This suggests that making generalizations depends more on a child’s cognitive development and reading experience than demographic variables. These results are consistent with Piñero and Cañedo’s (2014) findings of no significant differences in concluding skills across similar groups, although Çiğdemiri and Akyolii (2022) reported significant differences in reading comprehension scores based on income levels.

Table 13

Difference in the Level of Reading Proficiency according to Sequencing when grouped and compared according to Sex, Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	89	54.93	.018	.985	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	73	54.86				
Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	87	53.26	-.929	.354	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	75	56.80				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	59	53.15	-.733	.465	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	103	55.90				
Number Siblings	Few	58	58.93	1.619	1.07	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	104	52.65				

Table 13 shows no significant difference in Grade 5 learners’ reading proficiency in sequencing when grouped by sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, or number of siblings, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance level. Males and females had nearly identical mean scores, and differences across other groups were minimal, indicating these variables do not meaningfully affect students’ ability to sequence information in reading. This suggests that learners generally have a similar skill level in organizing reading details. These results align with Piñero and Cañedo’s (2014) findings of no significant differences in sequencing ability across similar demographic groups, though Cadiz-Gabejan and Quirino (2021) noted some variation in reading proficiency related to sex and parental education.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Academic Performance when grouped and compared according to Sex, Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment, and Average Family Monthly Income

Table 14

Difference in the Level of Academic Performance when grouped and compared according to Sex, Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment, Average Family Monthly Income, and Number of Siblings

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	89	57.22	.988	.324	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	73	54.85				
Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	87	54.00	-1.940	0.54	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	75	58.64				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	59	54.95	-.773	.441	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	103	56.84				

Number of Siblings	Few	58	60.65	2.732	.007	Significant
	Many	104	53.64			

Table 14 shows that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of Grade 4 learners when grouped by sex, parents' highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income, as all p-values exceeded the 0.05 significance level, supporting the null hypothesis. This suggests that these demographic factors have minimal influence on learners' academic outcomes and that the effect of poverty on educational achievement is less evident in this context. However, a significant difference was found when grouped by the number of siblings, with learners having fewer siblings performing better—supported by a p-value of 0.007. These findings align with Nyarko et al. (2018), who found no gender-based academic performance differences, and with Agiboshim and Obinna (2023), who reported that sibling structure significantly impacts academic outcomes. The results also partly support Sumugat and Caraballe's (2021) findings on the influence of family income on academic performance, though in this study, the impact was less pronounced.

Relational Analysis between the Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 4 Learners and their Level of Academic Performance

Table 15
Relationship Between the Level of Reading Proficiency of Grade 4 Learners and their Level of Academic Performance

Variables	N	r	p-value	Level of Significance	of Interpretation
Level of Reading Proficiency	162	.836	.000	.005	Significant
Level of Academic Performance	162				

Table 15 reveals a strong, significant positive relationship between Grade 4 learners' reading proficiency and their academic performance, with a Pearson r value of .836 and a p-value of .000, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates that students who read more efficiently tend to perform better academically, as continuous reading enhances vocabulary and comprehension crucial for understanding school concepts. This finding aligns with previous studies (Chege, 2014; Nyarko et al., 2018; Tagaytay, 2021; Ercikan et al., 2015; Onkoba, 2014) showing that higher reading proficiency correlates with better academic outcomes (Cadiz-Gabejan & Quirino, 2021), and highlights the importance of skills like noting details, sequencing, main idea identification, and predicting (Cimmiyotti, 2014; Anyienda et al., 2020). However, it contrasts with Iman's (2016) study, which suggests that reading comprehension skills do not significantly explain poor academic performance.

Conclusions:

The study found that most Grade 4 learners were male, from higher-income families, with parents having lower educational backgrounds and multiple siblings. Their reading proficiency was generally at the instructional level for skills like noting details and making inferences but remained at the frustration level for predicting outcomes, generalizing, and sequencing events. When categorized by sex, family income, and number of siblings, learners still demonstrated frustration-level reading proficiency, especially among those from lower-income families. Academic performance across the first and second quarters of the 2022–2023 school year was rated satisfactory, with no significant differences observed when grouped by sex, parents' education, or income, indicating uniform academic outcomes across demographic variables. However, notable differences in reading proficiency were observed in relation to parents' education, family income, and number of siblings, especially in noting details and making inferences. A significant relationship was also found between reading proficiency and academic performance, reinforcing the importance of strong literacy skills for overall academic success. These findings highlight the urgent need for targeted reading interventions, regardless of demographic background, and suggest that improving reading proficiency can have a direct impact on academic outcomes. Recommended actions include peer tutoring, dedicated reading periods, teacher training, development of localized reading materials, community involvement through reading corners, and the establishment of school libraries to foster a reading-rich environment.

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